

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF SMALL HYDROPOWER ON RIVER HYDROECOLOGY (ICHTHYOFAUNA) IN KOKSUV RIVER

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7183883>

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Abstract: *Identification of mountain and sub-mountain streams - small rivers suitable for rapid development of small hydropower plants (SHP) in the Republic of Uzbekistan and in order to evaluate their hydroecology retrospectively and the level of study of their current state, the river ichthyofauna was studied from the hydro-ecological parameters of the Koksuv River in the Shahimardan aclave, which is one of the enclaves of our country, and where the Shahimardon small hydroelectric power station is planned to be built and put into operation in the next few years and the effects of the small hydroelectric power station on them were considered.*

Keywords: *small hydropower, hydroecology, pollution, impact, ichthyofauna.*

Enter. Rivers are highly polluted by agricultural runoff, stormwater, and municipal wastewater. In addition to such effects, the hydro-ecology of rivers is also negatively affected by the hydrotechnical structures built by mankind, in particular, the hydroelectric power industry, which is one of the branches of electricity production, also produces electricity by damming the river beds in our country. , we witnessed the extremely high negative impact of these structures on hydroecology, not only on hydroecology, but also on all sectors of the economy, as we witnessed in the example of the Sardoba reservoir. In order to eliminate these situations, today in our country and all over the world, instead of using large hydroelectric power stations, small hydroelectric power stations are being used. Studies were conducted to study the impact of these small hydroelectric power stations (KGES) on hydroecology.

Relevance of the topic. Shakhimardon SHP is planned to be put into operation in the settlement of Shakhimardon enclave, which is surrounded by the Kyrgyz Republic in the Fergana region of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In 1998, it was determined that there was no reliable source of electricity to eliminate the consequences of the flood that occurred in the village of Shahimardan, and with the minutes of the government meeting

of the organizing committee for the elimination of the consequences of the natural disaster, the river was dammed in the village of Shahimardan. In 2008, a decision was made to ensure the construction of the SHP (in Koksuv).

Construction was stopped in 2005 due to problems with the transportation of materials and equipment across the state border, and the equipment was installed at another SHP.

At the moment, the situation in the rural area has significantly improved, and a decision was made to complete the construction of the Shahimardan SHP.

This SHP can produce energy by installing two generators of 1.05 MW each.

Shahimardan has a population of about 7,000 (2022), 93 recreation centers, 9 children's recreation centers, a tuberculosis hospital and other electricity consumers are operating. In addition, many tourists come to Shahimardan for recreation in the summer, and the population increases significantly during the summer season.

Currently, power supply to the Shahimardan enclave is carried out at a voltage of 35 kV from the Shahimardan substation with a single 1.6 MW transformer connected to the Kyrgyz power system through a 12.4 km overhead line with a cross section of AS-35. There are no other electricity generating enterprises in the considered area.

Power consumption at the node is more than 5 million kWh. The maximum electrical load is observed in the amount of 1.5 MW.

During the autumn-winter season, the Kyrgyz energy system periodically disconnects Shahimardan consumers according to the load limiting schedule.

Thus, at present, the consumers of Shahimardan are not provided with reliable electricity supply, and in order to ensure the necessary reliability, the construction of an additional network or the commissioning of the node's own production capacity is required.

Hydropower potential of the river basin. The Koksuv River, which is used in the construction of the SHP, will meet the enclave's need for electricity in the short term.

Materials and methods.

Field experiments were carried out from August of the summer season of 2021 to April of the spring season of 2022. We selected 9 main points from the section of the Koksuv River and 2 additional points along the length of the Aksuv River (Fig. 1).

The hydroecology (ichthyofauna) of the river was studied every month in the Shahimardan enclave, except for the winter season (it was not possible to visit due to the cold weather).

Figure 1. Designated points for research

In studying the hydroecology of the Koksuv River, we first studied the ichthyofauna of the river using a mordushka (wire net trap). When using this method, the results of the hydroecology of the river could not be fully and accurately studied. The reason for this is that the traps are not suitable for all fish species in the river and cannot cover them in full. However, we identified the first samples of river ichthyofauna using this method.

Studying ichthyofauna with Mordushka takes a long time, but it is completely harmless for the hydroecology of rivers, in this method, fish enter the trap made of wire mesh through a conical passage and cannot get out of the trap.

This trap is placed on the banks of the river with a low current, fully submerged, and after each night it is checked whether the fish have fallen into the trap.

Figure 2. Mordushka
Study of river hydroecology by electrofishing method.

In order to fully study the ichthyofauna of the Shahimardan River, we used the electrofishing method, which is a

novelty in our country and widely used in European countries for scientific purposes. Before using this method, we received permission to use the equipment by applying an official letter to the State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Identification of ichthyofauna by electrofishing method.

The ichthyofauna of Shahimardan was effectively studied using an electrofishing device, with the help of this method, existing fish in the river can be preserved and protected as carefully as possible. In this method, electricity is used to attract and stun the fish. Under the influence of electric current, the muscles of the fish contract, and the phenomenon of electrotaxis with the fish occurs, and the fish line up in a certain line in the electric field. Using this method does not kill the fish and even their seeds are not damaged. Using the electrofishing method requires three people:

- 1-Electrofishing user;
- 2-Retrieving fish from the water with a net;
- 3-Fish collector.

Figure 3. The process of studying the hydroecology of the Shahimardan River using electrofishing equipment. 1- Electrofishing user; 2- Catching fish from water with a net; 3- Fish collector; 4-Electrofishing equipment.

Results. In the process of checking the points that we determined in the study of the impact of SHP on the hydroecology of the river, it was found that there are fish species in the Shahimardan river, it should be emphasized that until now, it was known that there were no fish species in this river in any official sources, and we found fish species in this river. We were among the first researchers to identify it.

This fish species is a cold water species called Snowtrout and is mainly found in India along the Himalayas from Kashmir to Bhutan at an altitude of 300-2810 m. The species is a bottom-dwelling oligophagous herbivorous

fish with a transverse lower mouth. Shahimardan river is a very good environment for this type of fish.

The next type of fish caught was the *Nemachilus*. The living conditions of the fish were determined and the types of food were determined and released back into the river (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. a) Snowtrout; b) *Nemachilus*; c) process of inspection of caught fish; d) releasing fish into the river.

Other than these two fish species, no other fish species were detected. Fish were caught from the main 4-5-6-7-8-9 points located in the Koksuv and Shahimardan rivers. Fish were also recorded from 2 additional points marked from Aksuv River. No fish species were detected from the main points 1-2-3. The main reason for this is the anthropogenic waterfall located at point 4, and the fish could not swim through it. 1967 (according to local residents) the river bed was changed with the help of explosives. The purpose of this change was to bring water to a small hydroelectric plant. According to the interview with the local elders, the river bed starts from the water intake point for the small hydroelectric power station, It was moved to the side of the water intake point in the distance to "Pansionat Margilon SS". As a result of the research, it was also found that the caught fish are local fish. This is because there is a hydroelectric power station

"Nurgazi" in the territory of Kyrgyzstan and a central water distribution hydrostation in the center of Kadamjoy district. As a result, the migration path of fish species to the upper reaches of the Shahimardan River is completely blocked, and fish from the lower reaches are now unable to reach the upper reaches of the Shahimardan River (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Kyrgyzstan. Central water distribution hydrostation in the center of Kadamjoy district N 40.07.647; E 071.43.450; height-1009 m.

As you can see from the pictures, the river is completely blocked for the flow of water and fish migration.

Summary

This pending hydroelectric power plant will alter the continuity of natural flows and cause the loss of downstream ecosystem services. Investigations have shown that the Shahimardan River is currently not used for fishing, which means that the ecosystem does not provide aquatic products to the community. Since the Kuksuv River is a very small river, studies of aquatic hydroecology have been conducted only for fish species, and information on other aquatic animals such as crabs and molluscs is not available. Therefore, only the loss of fish species was considered in this study relative to the category of aquatic animals. There is also a possibility of river water build-up as a result of maximizing the economic benefit from the SHP.

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